

SCHEMATIC INTERVENTION: A TOOL FOR THE IMPROVEMENT OF READING COMPREHENSION OF GRADE 5 PUPILS IN A SELECT PUBLIC SCHOOL IN INFANTA, QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the improvement of reading comprehension among Grade Five pupils in Binulasan Integrated School as a basis in creating a schematic intervention for School Year 2022-2023. Fifteen (15) reader pupils in Grade Five were randomly selected as respondents and they were divided into five groups for the experimental research. Quasi-experimental design using quantitative measure was employed in this study to detect changes in the reading comprehension competence. These measures were administered on a pre-test and post-test basis before and after the schematic intervention. Data gathered were statistically treated using t-test, mean percentage and standard deviation to measure the effectiveness of the schematic intervention. The results revealed that the schematic intervention enhanced the comprehension level of the students than just reading a text. Thus, the schematic intervention found to be effective and can be used to enhance the reading comprehension of grade 4 pupils particularly in noting details, doing jotting down and highlighting. For getting the main idea, all the three schemes used were found to be effective, they are using anchor chart, interactive pictures, and adding the missing title. Next is for predicting outcomes, visualizing and comprehension monitoring. Then, in sequencing events, using video clips, and graphic organizer, also, signal words on the story board, all the three used schemes are effective. Lastly, cause and effect, the effective schemes are supplying connecting words and arranging jumbled words. This implies that teachers may utilize the proposed schematic intervention designed to improve the development of reading comprehension level of pupils.

Keywords: *Schematic Intervention, Reading Comprehension, Reading Skill*

INTRODUCTION

Without comprehension, reading is a frustrating, pointless exercise in word calling. It is no exaggeration to say that how well students develop the ability to comprehend what they read has a profound effect on their entire lives. A major goal of reading comprehension instruction, therefore, is to help students develop the knowledge, skills, and experiences they must have if they are to become competent and enthusiastic readers. Hence, teachers have a pivotal role in helping children to develop and maintain a positive attitude towards learning and literacy. Motivated readers read more, use more complex cognitive strategies, and thus become better readers.

In addition, reading comprehension has been a major point of focus for a variety of educational researchers throughout history. Poor reading Skill is manifested with poor comprehension, wrong pronunciations among others. If no proper intervention is administered early, it could affect the academic, social and psychological development of the child. As such, proper and correct diagnosis of reading disability as early as possible appears to be essential (Porqueriño, 2019)

To address the existing challenge, providing for quality education is one of the most important legacies the State and the local government can offer to the people, in ensuring the grant of good education to the children. Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, an act instituting a framework of governance of basic education, establishing authority and accountability, renaming the department of education, culture and sports as the department of education, and for other.

To get a decent education is one of the fundamental rights of every citizen. Thus, Section 2, Article XIV of our constitution imposes upon the State the responsibility to “protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels” and “take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all”. This bill aims to promote compulsory education for the children of compulsory school age, providing only for limited special circumstances for exemption, directing the local government units, particularly in the barangay level, to be directly involved in monitoring of the education of children under their areas of jurisdiction and the Department of Education to formulate the necessary curriculum for learning. For this purpose it shall be the joint responsibility of the Department of Interior and Local Government and the Department of Education to ensure the establishment of schools and the necessary support services for the implementation of this measure.

In line with the problem about reading comprehension, there are many schematic interventions that can be practiced to enhance the reading comprehension skills of the students such as comparing and contrasting, sequencing events in a story, analyzing the main idea of a text, understanding the author's purpose. interpreting context clues, making inferences and separating fact from opinion. These skills provide students with an opportunity to increase reading, writing, test taking, and study skills at their instructional level.

In the study of (Lemmello, 2021) a key aspect of reading intervention is developing self-esteem through acquisition of reading and writing skills and strategies. Students gain confidence and their skills improve through instruction in decoding, comprehension, writing, study skills, and test taking strategies across our school district curricula and units of study. Students read fiction and nonfiction books that are chosen to dovetail with the regular class curricula but are written at the students' instruction level. Students also have many opportunities to write in response to reading. Students who attend reading intervention are part of a community of learners who have an opportunity to increase their skills to become strong and confident readers and writers.

Research Questions

This research study aimed to develop a schematic intervention for the improvement of reading comprehension of Grade Five pupils in Binulasan Integrated School. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of reading comprehension among Grade Five pupils before the implementation of the schematic intervention?
2. What is the level of reading comprehension among Grade Five pupils after the implementation of the schematic intervention?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of the reading comprehension before and after the implementation of the schematic intervention among Grade Five pupils?
4. Based on the findings of this research study, what effective schematic intervention may be proposed for Grade Five pupils for the development of their reading comprehension?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Quasi-experimental approach using quantitative measure was designed to detect changes in the reading comprehension competence. These measures were administered on a pre-test and post-test basis before and after the schematic intervention.

This research used pre-test and post-test result using five comprehension skills. The instrument were used to determine the effectiveness of schematic interventions in developing reading comprehension level of grade 5 learners in Binulasan Integrated School.

Sampling

The present study utilized a random sampling method. The 15 respondent learners were randomly selected by the researcher with the help of their advisers, they were divided into five groups for the five reading comprehension skills. Each group has 3 members and each member used different intervention scheme.

Data Gathering Procedure

The undertaken survey has 5 groups of respondents for each comprehension skills, and each group has 3 pupils for each schemes.

Every group did the survey for three different weeks. One week for each group. During the scheduled week for each group, the pre-test was given, and with an interval time of one week, the post-test happened.

The following steps were undertaken by the researcher in order to gather data:

1. The researcher asked the permission to conduct the study to the Principal of Binulasan Integrated School, to the parents as well as to the pupil-respondents.
2. The researcher begins the pre-test, and after a week the post-test happened.
3. All the gathered data were treated and analysed using appropriate statistical tools

Research Instrument

The researchers constructed a researchers-made instrument on schematic intervention that served as the main tool in gathering the data needed in this survey study.

It consists of five skills: the sequencing events, getting the main idea, noting details, predicting outcomes, and cause and effect. Each skill has three schemes.

In sequencing events, there are three schemes used. These were: using video clips, graphic organizer, and signal word on the story board.

For getting the main idea, the schemes used were: anchor charts, interactive pictures, and adding the missing title.

Then, the noting details, the schemes were: using power point presentation, jotting down and highlighting.

Another was predicting outcomes, the three schemes were: directed reading thinking activity (DRTA), visualizing, and comprehension monitoring.

And lastly, the cause and effect, the schemes were: using pictures, supplying connecting words, and arranging jumbled words.

All the five comprehension skills were measuring the same competency which was to develop understanding from the text read.

Statistical Treatment

1. Mean percentage of scores was used to determine the comprehension level of selected the Grade 5 pupils.

$$WM = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum x$ = summation of weighted frequencies

N = number of cases

2. The t-test for correlated sample was utilized to determine if difference exists between pre-test and post-test.

Where :

x1=mean difference of table 1

x2= mean difference of table 2

S2=standard error of the difference the two means

N=number

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter covers the results and discussions concerning the reading comprehension level and schematic intervention used to Grade 5 learners in Binulasan integrated school.

The order of the discussion follows the arrangement of the Statement of the Problem in Chapter 1.

1.1. Reading Comprehension Before and After the Schematic Intervention

Implementations of appropriate intervention have significant impact to the pupils. In this regard, it is really important that every learner can fully acquire the set of reading skills/competencies per grade level to be able to utilize that in getting information, understanding written text and concepts, conveying messages and eventually developing these competencies needed in the other learning areas, Cando (2018).

Reading Comprehension Before and After the Schematic Intervention

Table 1

SEQUENCING EVENTS		
Schemes	Pre-test	Post-test
Video Clips	5	5
Graphic Organizer	3	5
Signal Words on the story board	5	5
Mean Score	4.33	5
GETTING THE MAIN IDEA		
Schemes	Pre-test	Post-test
Anchor chart	5	5
Interactive Picture	1	5
Add the Missing Title	3	5
Mean Score	3	5
NOTING DETAILS		
Schemes	Pre-test	Post-test
Power Point Presentation	1	4
Jotting Down	5	5
Highlighting	4	5
Mean Score	3.33	4.67
PREDICTING OUTCOMES		
Schemes	Pre-test	Post-test
Directed Reading Thinking Activity (DRTA)	4	4
Visualizing	1	3
Comprehension Monitoring	3	5
Mean Score	2.67	4
CAUSE AND EFFECT		
Schemes	Pre-test	Post-test
Using Picture	2	3
Supplying Connecting Words	1	2
Jumbled Words	2	5
Mean Score	1.67	3.33
Overall Mean Score	3	4.44

Table 1 presents the comparison reading comprehension before and after the schematic intervention. It shows that during the pre-test, the results of the scores of pupils vary from each other. There are pupils appeared to have highest or perfect score even without schematic intervention as showed in the graph. But still there is more number of pupils who got low scores, means they need to have intervention. While in the post-test most number of pupils got highest or perfect score. Since, the post-test schematic intervention was conducted. However, there was 1 pupil who still got the low score in the

post test, shows that schematic intervention being used to that pupil is not that effective than the other interventions used.

However, it shows that doing the schematic intervention turned out to be effective as appeared in the study. There are 5 reading comprehension skills and each skill has 3 interventions scheme/schematic intervention used. Furthermore, as the result of the study, in noting detail skills, the schemes are using power point presentation, the pupil doing the test got the score of 1 in the pre-test and 4 in the post-test, while, in jotting down the pupil got 5 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test and in highlighting the pupil got 4 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test and it shows that among the three schemes jotting down and highlighting are found to be more effective.

In getting the main idea, the schemes are using anchor chart which the pupils got the score of 5 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test. In using interactive picture, the pupils got 1 score in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test, while in add the missing title; the pupils got 3 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test. It appears that all the schemes used are effective.

For predicting outcomes, the schemes used are the directed thinking reading activity (DRTA), the pupils got the score of 4 in the pre-test and 4 in the post-test, while, visualizing, the students got 1 in the pre-test and 3 in the post-test, and comprehension monitoring, the students got 3 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test. The result shows that visualizing and comprehension monitoring are the effective schemes to be used to pupils.

In sequencing events, the schemes used are using video clip the pupil got the test score of 5 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test. In using graphic organizer, the pupil got 3 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test, while in using signal words in the story board, the students got 5 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test. It found out that using all the schemes for the sequencing skill found to be effective.

And lastly, the cause and effect skills, the schemes are using pictures, the pupil got the score of 2 in the pre-test and 3 in the post-test. In supplying connecting words, the pupil got 1 in the pre-test and 2 in the post-test, while in using jumbled words, the pupils got 2 in the pre-test and 5 in the post-test. The result of the scores shows that supplying connecting words and arranging jumbled words found more effective schemes.

The result of the study was supported by Cabardo (2015), stated that it is recommended for teachers to develop reading intervention programs, device of localized and contextualized reading materials, text and selection will ensure the development of the reading proficiency of the students.

Significant difference between before and after the implementation of the schematic intervention

Reading Intervention provides students with an opportunity to increase reading, writing, test taking, and study skills at their instructional level. A key aspect of

reading intervention is developing self-esteem through acquisition of reading and writing skills and strategies. Students gain confidence and their skills improve through instruction in decoding, comprehension, writing, study skills, and test taking strategies across our school district curricula and units of study (Lemello, 2021).

Table 2 presents the results of analysis on the significant difference between before and after the implementation of the schematic intervention.

Table 2

Significant difference between before and after the implementation of the schematic intervention

Test	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Pre-test	3.00	1.60	-	0.00	Reject Null Hypothesis	Significantly Different
Post test	4.40	0.99	4.1762			

Note: Level of significance at 5%

As can be gleaned from table 2, pre-test has a mean of 3.0 with the standard deviation of 1.60, while post-test has a mean of 4.40 with the standard deviation of 0.99. With the t-value of -4.1762 and p-value of 0.00 implies that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between before and after the implementation of the schematic intervention is hereby rejected. Hence, the mean difference of 1.4 between before and after the implementation of the schematic intervention is found to be significant. The scores of post-testis more homogeneous compared to pre-test which implies that post-test scores are relatively closed with each other compared to pre-test scores.

In one study, it was found out that different reading strategies were pointed out as effective for reading comprehension. Also, the study of Oxford (2018), found out that through regular practice and using 12 reading strategies can help struggling readers improve their reading comprehension. It was also said that students can improve their expository text comprehension when given some intervention like using graphic organizer and other interventions that would help the needs of the pupils.

On the other hand, Zimmerman (2019), said that visualization is creating fun illustrations and being able to visualize what was read can help them digest the writing better. For in the conducted research study found out that visualization got the lowest score even in the post-test or after the schematic intervention which is visualization.

Proposed Schematic Interventions

As the result of the survey, the effective schematic intervention to enhance the reading comprehension of grade 5 pupils that found out in the result of the survey are; in noting details, doing jotting down and highlighting were the effective schemes, and using power point presentation was the least effective among the tree used scheme.

For getting the main idea, all the three used intervention schemes used are effective, they are using anchor chart, interactive pictures, and adding the missing title.

In predicting outcomes skill, among the three schemes, directed thinking reading activity was rejected for having the least effective survey result, and visualizing and comprehension monitoring are the effective intervention schemes.

Then, in sequencing events, using video clips, and graphic organizer and signal words on the story board, all the three used schemes are effective.

Lastly, cause and effect, the effective schemes are supplying connecting words and arranging jumbled words. While, using picture was resulted for being not that effective intervention scheme.

Conclusions

In light of the findings aforesaid the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The reading comprehension level among the grade 5 pupils in Binulasan Integrated School had a fairly satisfactory level in the pre-test.
2. Most of the pupil-respondents were able to comprehend better with the text read after the schematic intervention.
3. There is a significant difference in the reading comprehension level of the respondents before and after the implementation of the schematic intervention. It proves that schematic interventions enhanced the reading comprehension level of grade 5 pupils in Binulasan Integrated School.

Recommendations

In light of the aforementioned findings and conclusions the following are hereby recommended:

1. To the teachers.

- a. Prepare and use reading materials suited to the comprehension level of the pupils
 - b. Allow pupils to explore and engage themselves to some reading activities.
 - c. Encourage and motivate pupils in the art of reading.
 - d. They must conduct more studies about reading interventions or strategies to be used to struggling in reading.
 - e. Monitor the reading comprehension level of the pupils and give immediate action to pupils encountering difficulties comprehending with the text.
2. To the parents.
 - a. Allow pupils to explore and engage themselves to some reading activities at home.
 - b. Always give time to your child to teach reading.
 - c. Monitor the child's progress in school.
 3. To the school administrator.
 - a. Encourage the teachers to attend trainings/seminars that will hone their knowledge in teaching reading comprehension to their pupils.
 - b. Monitor the teachers' status regarding the reading development of the pupils they handled.
 4. To the Department of Education.
 - a. Conduct more training/seminars for teachers on how to teach and enhance the reading comprehension of the pupils/students they handled.
 - b. Allocate enough budget for the reading materials to support the Childs need to learn how to read.
 5. To the future researchers.
 - a. They could replicate this study and do further research regarding the schematic intervention that can be used to pupils/students in every school.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers sought an approval first from their school head, next was getting permission from the parents and pupils stating the areas and data they needed before answering the questionnaire survey. Meanwhile, the researchers guaranteed that all the answers and responses of the respondent learners remained confidential since the researchers did not involve their family background information to secure their confidentiality and anonymity.

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